

Problem Faced by the Mango Exporters during COVID-19 in Pakistan

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Abstract:

The current research investigates Problem faced by the Mango Exporters during COVID-19 in Pakistan. Data were collected from 40 Mango growers in Tando jam and Tando Allahyar. Data were analyzed by using SPSS-24 version. It was revealed that during covid-19 shortage of skill labor, because most of the labour came from Punjab and during lockdown unavailability of skill labour in these districts. It was further revealed that shortage of water, lack of raw materials, inadequate logistics, High costs of production, lack of policy support from Government and quartine problem were identified.

Keywords: Mango Exporters, COVID-19 in Pakistan

Introduction:

The export of mangoes from Pakistan would commence from May 20, 2019, during the current season while the export target of mangoes has been set as 100,000 metric tons. Pakistan expects a generous revenue through the export of mangoes keeping in view the devaluation of the currency against the dollar coupled with the export of mangoes during the fasting month. According to experts, climate change and global warming are serious potential threats to the production of mangoes and due to its negative impact, the overall production of mangoes was 50 per cent less than last year while it's continued negative impact is anticipated to lead to 35 per cent lesser production. Due to acute shortage of water, mango orchards in Sindh which includes Hyderabad District, Tando Allahyar, Mirpur Khas are to be severely affected. The same goes to Punjab where the overall production of mangoes is anticipated to less by 30 to 50 per cent in mango growing areas including Muzzafar Garh, Multan, Rahim Yar Khan, and Shujabad. Simultaneously with lesser production, the smaller size of mangoes is also of great concern to the exporters. Due to increase in demand and shortage of supply this year, the wholesale price of mangoes is expected to increase from Rs2,400 to Rs3,000 per 40 kg.

According to the private and public sector stakeholders, the most significant problems that affect the mango value chain in Sindh have are as follows:

- . a) Lack of know-how (e.g. lack of trade and marketing information; inadequate management; language barriers);
- . b) Low volumes (e.g. low export volumes; lack of raw materials; ageing of orchards; growing urbanization);
- . c) Poor quality (e.g. fruit fly infestation; irregularity of products);
- . d) Inadequate logistics (e.g. lack of infrastructure; lack of specialized transportation of fresh fruits)
- . e) High costs of production (e.g. packaging; energy, inputs); and
- . f) Lack of organization (e.g. no stakeholders' consultations; lack of policy support).

Strengths and opportunities of the mango value chain are:

- . a) Taste of mango;
- . b) Good quality of specific varieties (i.e. Sindhri, and langar)
- . c) Diversity of mango varieties;
- . d) Existence of growing market for good quality mango.

The region should seize the opportunity to target export market with quality tasteful varieties of fresh mango from Sindh and domestic and regional markets with second and third quality mango. In order to do s must be able to:

- Deliver quality products at affordable prices,
- Provide adequate quantities of all varieties of mango,
- Reduce logistic costs; and
- Improve management.

Solutions

Strategies

Market Linkage

Export oriented Strategies

Value Addition

By Products of Mango

Achar, Tin Pack mango

IMPACT 1: Increase the value added of mango production, in order to contribute substantially to poverty reduction; and IMPACT 2: Increase the value added of marketed mango, in order to improve wealth creation, economical growth and competitiveness.

To achieve these impacts and following the log frame framework, the strategy is based on five intermediary goals that were validated by stakeholders:

Goal 1: Increase mango production; Goal 2: Reduce post-harvest losses; Goal 3: Increase the volume of the first quality mango exported; Goal 4: Increase the volume of second quality mango sold on the local market; and Goal 5: Increase the volume of the industrial category used for processing

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Conclusions: The current research investigates the problems and challenges faced by mango Exporter during cOVID-19 pandemic. Due to acute shortage of water, mango orchards in Sindh which includes Hyderabad District, Tando Allahyar, Mirpur Khas are to be severely affected. The same goes to Punjab where the overall production of mangoes is anticipated to less by 30 to 50 per cent in mango growing areas including Muzzafar Garh, Multan, Rahim Yar Khan, and Shujabad. Simultaneously with lesser production, the smaller size of mangoes is also of great concern to the exporters. Due to increase in demand and shortage of supply this year.

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